
Road Safety: An Interdisciplinary Research and Training to Save Humanity

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Abstract:

A road accident is considered a major global problem because it results in a significant number of fatalities and injuries worldwide every year, making it a leading cause of death, particularly among young people, and posing a significant public health concern across different regions; with factors like speeding, drunk driving, distracted driving, and poor road infrastructure contributing to the issue. Road safety is an effort to minimize the accidents and accidents severity by taking precautions before accidents as measures of preparedness, steps just during accidents and analysis and improvements after accidents. Road safety required interdisciplinary knowledge in pre accident period to prepare to reduce accidents and its severity, during accident to stop fatalities and serious injuries and after accident for corrective measures to avoid future accidents, and to minimize ill effects of accidents. Hence it is a collaborative effort that involves multiple disciplines to improve road safety. In different road safety models strategy includes '5E' Engineering, Enforcement, Education, Emergency medical services and Empathy of Human.

Enforcement is strictly enforcing traffic laws to deter speeding and drunk driving, wrong side driving, overloading of commercial vehicle etc. Engineering of road and vehicle aim to improve roads and vehicles to avoid accidents and fatalities and serious injuries, Improve road conditions, signage, lighting, and design of road and vehicles both .Education and awareness is to educate road users about the risks of speeding, drunk driving, and distracted driving, it also involves to educate peoples about traffic rules and road signage and markings. Similarly Emergency medical trauma services are to ensure emergency services are available and responsive. Empathy or behavior change to encourage road users to wear seat belts, helmets, and child restraints, and to avoid drinking and distractions while driving to avoid accidents.

Thus in road safety multi disciplines required to collaborate together with interdisciplinary knowledge to prepare for accidents which may occur, quick action during accidents and analysis and improvements after accidents. Different government, public sector and private stake holders responsible for road safety have to educate and train in different disciplines to minimize the effect of road accidents. Similarly different NGOs and volunteers required multidisciplinary training and interdisciplinary action to cater awareness and to help victims of accidents during and after accidents. Most important road users and drivers also required multi discipline education and training and training to take interdisciplinary action to overcome severity of road accidents and to reduce loss of property and life in accidents which is not a national but a global challenge. By taking steps towards interdisciplinary research, education and training accidents cannot stop but losses of accidents can be reduce significantly.

Key Words: Road Safety, Accident, Road, Vehicle, Engineering, Education, Enforcement, Emergency, Interdisciplinary

Introduction:

Road safety refers to the measures taken to reduce the risk of road traffic injuries and fatalities, including different aspects as safe road engineering or road infrastructure, vehicle engineering, safe driving practices, traffic regulations and emergency trauma facilities. Road safety is integrated action of multidiscipline together to reduce injuries and deaths in road accidents. There are different stake holders involve in road safety work together, hence they required to train them with interdisciplinary knowledge. To gather interdisciplinary knowledge it need of hours to create and develop sufficient

training modules with thorough interdisciplinary knowledge. This research paper emphasizes the need of an interdisciplinary research and training to save humanity by preparing stakeholders mindset and motivations to work in an interdisciplinary environment with multidisciplinary knowledge. It will help us to take essential measures pre, during and post road accidents.

Problems and Objectives:

Road accidents are catastrophic global problem. Million peoples kill in road accident in few decades worldwide. Global scenario is that in year 2023 total 12 lakh People died in road accidents all

over the world and many more severely injured and get permanent disability. In country like India, accidents are similar to national catastrophic loss in which most of the young and working generation suffered more. In year 2023 total 4.8 lakh accidents occurred in which total fatality is 1.73 lakh while total injury is 4.63 lakh. Similarly data of a single state Uttar Pradesh in India shows that total 2400 people were killed in road accidents along with 31000 people severely injured or got permanent disability in total 44000 accidents. Hence Road Accident is a Global problem to find out the solution to save properties and human life, over all to save the humanity. This research paper is an effort to emphasize that how road accident can reduced and victims of road accident suffer less.

Scope and Limitations:

There is Much more Opportunities and challenges while working in road safety with aim of reduction of road accidents and mitigation of road accident victims along with preparedness for future to break the chain of similar accidents. The entire subject cannot address in few words hence this article is limited to study about the scope of research and training to save life in road accidents. Basically Road Safety study, research and training is not a single direction, single subject or single focus action. It is a multidimensional or multi-disciplinary research and study with interdisciplinary relationship and understanding.

Methodology:

Road Safety is multi-disciplinary task with interdisciplinary knowledge. There are '4E' Suggested by working committee of Ministry of Road Transport and Highway (MoRTH) government of India. Engineering, Education, Enforcement and Emergency care. Global scenario is that there are '6E' including '2E' apart from that suggested by MoRTH are Environment and Empathy. Trainer, trainee and researchers interested to work in field of road safety required to learn about all 'Es' related to road safety.

Engineering (Road & Vehicle): Knowledge of basic road engineering, road markings and signs are essential knowledge required to work in road safety field. Different countries have their own guidelines regarding Road Engineering. Engineering of Vehicle related to shape size and loading and environmental aspects. It is a pre accident task.

Education (and Awareness): Education and awareness is necessary for every citizen for safer roads driving and usages. Trainee and Researcher must know the points of education and awareness. This is a pre accident task.

Enforcement: Enforcement is to enforcing laws over road user. If someone is not aware and careless at road then law must be binding upon him to save others life.

Emergency Care: It is Post accident subject to save the road accident victims with care required golden hours. All type of medical facilities and first aid should be arranged and knowledge of primary usage of these facilities required for all stake holders of road safety committee.

Environment: Environment related to road accidents are not only weather condition But it also includes facilities over road and driving conditions, road markings and signage over road.

Empathy: Empathy related to social participation without which all type of facilities will be worthless. So, we can say that multi-disciplinary knowledge and interdisciplinary action is needed in road safety.

Conclusions:

1. In this study it can be concluded that Multi-disciplinary knowledge required for training and research with interdisciplinary implementation. It can be noted that:-Road Safety is a multi-disciplinary task required multi-disciplinary knowledge.
2. Inter disciplinary action is required during accident; hence interdisciplinary action must care during training and research.
3. Road Engineers must understand the other factors like emergency care, vehicle engineering effect of environment, empathy etc.
4. Police and Transport authorities must have basic knowledge of road and vehicle engineering, education and awareness facts, emergency care, environment and public empathy for better results.
5. Hence it can be concluded that multi-disciplinary knowledge and interdisciplinary action is the primary requirement of road safety training and research to save not only life and property but overall humanity, because death or injuries causing permanent disabilities have longer effect on not only the suffered family but over the prosperity of any nation. Hence this global problem can be taken with planned multidisciplinary knowledge with scope of interdisciplinary action through planned training and research. Different stakeholders responsible are needs to train and to motivate to research and to develop multidisciplinary knowledge and to be prepare to work in interdisciplinary environment to reduce injuries and deaths during road accidents.

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